

NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MATHEMATICAL
ADVANCES (NCMA 2025)

7– 8 April 2025, St Joseph's University, Bengaluru,
India.

GENERALIZATIONS OF HURTWITZ
BASIS THEOREM FOR GROUP
DIAGRAMS EMBEDDED IN R^n SPACE

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Abstract

Geometric Group Theory is a field that studies symmetries in Mathematical Structures in a combinatorial method that provides an intuitive and sometimes visually appealing study.

A group diagram or a cayley diagram is a graph where the vertices are the elements of the finite group and the edges are the generators of the finite group.

The Heegaard genus of a closed, orientable 3-manifold M , denoted by $g(M)$, is the smallest genus of any Heegaard splitting of M . A *Heegaard splitting* is a decomposition of M into two handlebodies H_1 and H_2 such that $H_1 \cap H_2$ is a common boundary surface of genus g .

Abstract

This paper is a rough sketch of a proof of a generalization of Hurwitz theorem that relates a group's order to the surface genus of its group diagram or Cayley graph

To do this we employ the use of Euler characteristic for polyhedron $V-E+F=2$ which we then roughly define for higher dimensional connected complexes or n -cells, which already exists as the topological generalization of Euler Characteristic.

A handlebody is like a surface with thickness. For example, a solid ball is a handlebody of genus 0, a solid torus (a thick donut) is a handlebody of genus 1, and a double torus with thickness is a handlebody of genus 2. It is the 3D version of a surface with holes.

Abstract

We then search for a suitable definition of higher dimensional genus so as to generalize our surface genus. We then construct our proof similar to how the Hurwitz basis was proven for 2d group diagrams (embedded in higher space depending on context) We then construct some cases to get basic info on the structure of the group by putting arbitrary values for the genus or number of generators

We finish with a proposal of Research groups being launched for topics like Tropical Geometry and Complex ordered differential equations

Keywords: Group Diagram, Euler Characteristic, Heegaard Genus, Geometric Group Theory

2020 AMS Subject Classification: 20F65

Introduction

This paper talks about topics in the field of combinatorial Group theory or geometric group theory.

A Group is a Mathematical structure observed in highly symmetrical structures and objects. They are defined as a set with a Binary operation that obeys rules like associativity, algebraic closure such that it has an identity element and an inverse for all elements.

NOTE: We may also use this definition for objects with unary operations by introducing a placeholder element.

Introduction

For this we use the Topological definition of the Euler Characteristic

The polyhedral surfaces discussed above are, in modern language, two-dimensional finite CW-complexes. (When only triangular faces are used, they are two-dimensional finite simplicial complexes.) For a simplicial complex, the **Euler characteristic** equals the alternating sum

$$\chi = C_0 - C_1 + C_2 - C_3 + \cdots ,$$

where C_n denotes the number of n -simplices in the complex.

Introduction

First we ask the question that what is the Hurwitz Theorem and why is it important.

Without the Hurwitz Theorem the Cayley graph is only useful as a pretty picture. Through the Hurwitz Theorem and its generalizations we may extend the study from just \mathbb{R}^3 embedded, finite Cayley graphs to \mathbb{R}^n embedded, finite Cayley graphs to perhaps infinite Group diagrams.

Cayley diagrams are also super useful in recognizing group structure outside math research. You may refer the Dehn publication for the proof of Hurwitz Theorem on the Order of Groups some of its conclusions are as follows:

Some Hurwitz results

1. If the surface genus $p \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$ then:

$$p \geq 1 + \frac{N}{4} \quad (1)$$

2. if the surface genus ≥ 1 and $n = 3$
such that exactly one generator has order 3
and the rest have order 2

$$p \geq 1 + \frac{N}{12} \quad (2)$$

Hurwitz basis for group diagram embedded in k -space dimensions

Let s_i be the generators of a finite group G , such that:

$$\exists m_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \forall s_i^{m_i} = 1$$

$$s_1^{m_1} = s_2^{m_2} = \dots = s_n^{m_n} = 1$$

$$V - E + F = 2$$

we know that

$$V - E + F = 2 - 2p$$

Hurtwitz basis for group diagram embedded in k -space dimensions

So the Euler Characteristic is valid for convex polyhedra, if we think about it the polyhedra itself acts as a 3-cell and the number of 3-cells, $C_3 = 1$ so we may claim that

$$V - E + F = 2 \longrightarrow V - E + F - 1 = 1$$

which becomes

$$V - E + F - C_3 = 1$$

our generalization proposes that

$$V - E + F - C_3 = 1 -$$

g_3

where g_3 is the Heegaard genus or we can claim that in general

$$\sum_{i=0}^k (-1)^i n_{\text{cell}} = \chi_k = 1 - g_{k-1}$$

Assuming the formula holds for Euler characteristic in 3-space:

$$\chi_3 = 1 - g_3$$

or in general

$$\chi_k = 1 - g_k$$

- ▶ Step 1: Take Euler characteristic
- ▶ Step 2: Define genus for 3-cell from k-cell
- ▶ Step 3: Perform triangulation (the method of counting used)

Generalization of Hurtwitz Theorem

There are two possibilities:

$$\sum_o^n (-1)^n (\text{n cell}) = 1 - g_3 \quad \text{or} \quad 1 - 2g_3$$

(1)

Assuming (1) to be true, let X_3 be the Euler characteristic in 3-space. For n -space, we define:

$$X_n = 1 - g_{n-1}$$

Generalization of Hurwitz Theorem

Let $N = |G|$ (Order of G).

$$V = N$$

$$E = N(n + 1)$$

$$F = N \left(1 - \sum \frac{1}{m_i} \right)$$

$$C_3 = N(?)$$

\vdots

$$C_n = N \cdot k_n$$

k_n is the counting coefficient

Generalization of Hurwitz Theorem

We may use

$$X_3 = V - E + F - C + 1 - g_h$$

Let $g_h = 0$ and manually compute for some example cases.

- ▶ Other combinatorial methods of forming subset cells.
- ▶ $g_h > 1$ and $n > 3$
- ▶ $g_h = 0$ Find bounds of n

Let $n = 1, 2 \dots$ or

$n \Rightarrow$ some upper bound.

- ▶ $g_h = 1$ and $m_i = m_j, \quad \forall i, j \leq 2+$

Justification for Embedding \mathbb{R}^n in Non-Euclidean Space

- ▶ In \mathbb{R}^2 : Angles Around a point Theorem states that the sum of angles around a point is 2π .
- ▶ Similarly, in \mathbb{R}^3 : $\sum \text{angles} = 4\pi$
- ▶ Generally, in \mathbb{R}^n : $\sum \text{angles} = \frac{2\pi^n}{\Gamma(n/2)}$
- ▶ For multiple k -cells tiling a k -subspace embedded in $\mathbb{R}^{n \geq k}$, the angle sum condition must be:

$$\sum \text{angles} > \frac{2\pi^n}{\Gamma(n/2)}$$

Tropical Geometry

Complex-Ordered Derivatives

Reference

1. Max Dehn(1987),Papers in Group Theory and Topology,Springer Verlag New-york.